

Frequency Domain Speckle Tracking for 3-D Vibrometry

Anna M. Wisniowiecki,^{1,2} Kumara Ratnayake², John S. Oghalai,^{2,3} and Brian E. Applegate^{2,3,a)}

¹ *Department of Biomedical Engineering, Texas A&M University, College Station, TX, 77843, USA*

² *Caruso Department of Otolaryngology – Head and Neck Surgery, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, CA 90033, USA*

³ *Alfred Mann Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, CA 90033, USA*

^{a)} Corresponding author: brianapp@usc.edu

Abstract. The organ of Corti performs complex 3D processing of sound waves to decompose and amplify sound, enabling accurate sound perception. However, the mechanism of cochlear amplification and mechanical role of cellular constituents remain unclear and difficult to study noninvasively. Vibrometry within the organ of Corti based on Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) has enabled new investigations of the cochlear mechanics in animal models of hearing. However, the current approach is limited to measuring motion along the optical axis of the imaging system, i.e. the z-component. Here we present initial work on a new approach based on frequency domain speckle tracking to extract the angle of motion in a given plane. By combining the angle of motion measured in x-z and y-z planes and the z-amplitude component, obtained using existing OCT-V, this method enables reconstruction of the vector of motion using a single optical axis OCT system. Preliminary results suggest that the angle of motion can be measured statistically based on our method with vibration amplitude sensitivity down to ~50 nm for a vibrating phantom at 100 Hz.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the scale and location of the inner ear, it is particularly difficult to observe the natural function of the cochlea noninvasively. Mammalian hearing relies on the propagation and transduction of a 3-dimensional (3D), spatially-tuned wave to achieve its specialized frequency range and tuning. Thus, to study the mechanisms of hearing in the cochlea, a noninvasive measure of vibration is critical. Optical coherence tomography (OCT) has filled this technology gap in otology research by providing noninvasive, depth-resolved imaging with micron-scale resolution and vibrometry with pico-meter scale sensitivity in the mammalian ear¹. Great progress has been made using OCT vibrometry (OCT-V) by enabling the direct measurement of the organ of Corti at acoustic frequencies²⁻⁴. Although OCT-V has advanced our ability to investigate the biophysical basis of hearing, current OCT-V remains limited to measuring vibration along one axis, resulting in conclusion uncertainty and measurement dependence on imaging angle⁵⁻⁷.

A measure of the 3D vibration vector is necessary to measure the mechanical role and relationship of cell types in the Organ of Corti and contribute physical evidence to the debate on potential mechanisms of hearing. We have addressed this previously by developing an OCT system with 3 optical axes such that the output could be transformed mathematically into a vector of motion⁸. Nevertheless, this approach is complex and requires a precise calibration so that the three volume images can be co-registered. The approach becomes particularly challenging when increasing the numerical aperture of the system to achieve cellular resolution because of the requirement that three independent beams scan the same volume.

Herein, we present a concept for a new approach to measuring the displacement vector using a single beam OCT system. We have developed a hybrid algorithm that combines typical OCT-V measurements of vibration amplitude

with measures of vibration angle based on the periodic change in the speckle pattern. We present numerical simulations showing this approach will work along with experimental verification in 2-D on tissue phantoms.

METHODS

By collecting sequential B-Scans of a sample region-of-interest (ROI) with a frame rate greater than the Nyquist frequency of the sample vibration, information about the vibration direction is directly encoded in an image stack. We propose to extract the angles of the 3D motion vector via the vibration-based modulation of the image spatial frequencies. Spatial frequencies along the axis of vibration undergo greatest modulation, while those along the perpendicular axis undergo the least. Thus, monitoring a vibrating sample over time, an axis of reduced spatial frequency content is observed in the spatial frequency map of the image at the modulation frequency which directly corresponds to the average vibration axis. Extending this concept to data collection in both the x-z and y-z plane, the angles of the 3D motion vector ($\Phi_{x,z}$ and $\Phi_{y,z}$) can be measured. Combining the angles of the 3D motion vector with the axial vibration amplitude (z) measured in existing OCT-V, we can reconstruct the vector of motion as shown in Equation 1.

$$\mathbf{v} = z/\tan(\Phi_{x,z})\hat{i} + z/\tan(\Phi_{y,z})\hat{j} + z\hat{k} \quad (1)$$

To test our concept, data was collected in the following way. An 800 nm spectral-domain OCT system with closely matched lateral and axial optical resolution ($\sim 2.4 \mu\text{m}$) was used to collect 2000 sequential OCT images over the same location in the x-z plane on a scattering tissue phantom (TiO_2 and optical epoxy, $n=1.56$). The frame rate was set to 833 Hz using a MEMS mirror. The tissue phantom was mounted on a piezoelectric stack and driven at 100 Hz using a function generator. Lateral oversampling was performed to satisfy the Nyquist theorem and resolve the speckle pattern; axial sampling was matched to this value. A rotation stage was used to collect data over a range of angles with vibration amplitudes ranging from 50 nm – 200 nm. Vibration amplitude and angle of incidence were confirmed by measuring M-Scans.

OCT B-Scans were processed according to conventional OCT processing. The B-Scan was then divided into $\sim 5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ regions of interest (ROIs) using a sliding window over the B-Scan. Subsequent processing was applied to each ROI to estimate the angle of motion. First, the image stack, $S(x,z,t)$, was filtered along the time axis around the stimulus frequency to yield the modulated image, $S(x,z,f_{\text{stim}})$. The 2-D fast Fourier transform (2D-FFT) of the modulated image was then calculated to yield $s(k_x, k_z, f_{\text{stim}})$. Figure 1 shows examples of the processed image series.

To measure the vibration axis from the experimental spatial frequency map, a line integral was calculated over the spatial frequency map at 0-180 degrees through zero to detect the axis of reduced image modulation. Based on our theory, the angle producing the minimum line integral is expected to match the vibration angle. Due to variability in the prediction over the B-Scan, we decided to utilize the unique representation of the modulated speckle content provided by the line integral curve (over degrees) to improve our prediction. We further simulated vibration using a frame captured at the ROI in order to compare the resulting line integral curves. The sample B-Scan was modulated sinusoidally in x and z directions using the reference M-Scan vibration amplitude and vibration angles ranging from 0-180 degrees according to Equation 2 and 3.

$$\Delta x = \frac{m}{dx} \sin(\alpha) \sin(2\pi ft) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta z = \frac{m}{dz} \cos(\alpha) \sin(2\pi ft) \quad (3)$$

Where Δx and Δz are the displacements over time in x and z, respectively, m is the vibration magnitude, dx and dz are the spatial sampling in the x and z directions respectively, α is the vibration angle, f is the vibration frequency and t is the time vector created using acquisition parameters to provide the same number of frames as the experimental dataset. The Δx and Δz displacement vectors were then used to interpolate the input B-Scan at each timepoint to create an image series with the desired modulation. The same post-processing as described above was then applied to the simulated data. A line integral through zero was calculated over each spatial frequency map from 0-180 degrees. Finally, the mean squared error was calculated between each resulting curve for simulated spatial frequency maps and the experimental spatial frequency map. The simulated vibration angle corresponding to the lowest mean squared error was chosen as the predicted vibration angle. The ground truth angle and amplitude from M-Scans were corrected for refractive index for comparison with estimated values.

FIGURE 1. a) Example ROI from a B-Scan of the tissue phantom with rotation angle of -18° . b) The corresponding image series was filtered around the vibration frequency to extract the vibration frequency image. c) The 2D-FFT of the vibration frequency image yields the spatial frequency map for a $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ ROI.

RESULTS

To assess the accuracy of the proposed method, we performed the above processing for ROIs over the entire B-scan using a sliding window. The red asterisks in Figure 2a show the center of each ROI. The ground truth vibration angle was subtracted from vibration angle predictions from each ROI to assess the vibration angle prediction error. The vibration angle prediction error was characterized as a function of vibration amplitude for several experimental vibration angles. The results for -9° and -18° vibration angles are displayed in boxplots in Figure 2b and 2c, respectively. It can be seen that the median vibration angle prediction is similar across vibration amplitude with low error. This implies that a statistical approach to the proposed method may yield an accurate prediction of the vibration angle. Prediction error and the standard deviation of the prediction error are observed to increase for lower vibration amplitudes for both vibration angles. This result is expected as the displacement decreases relative to the optical resolution and sampling of the speckle pattern.

FIGURE 2. Mean B-Scan for -18° rotation angle with ROI center points labeled (a). Each center is labeled with red asterisk. Vibration angle was predicted for each ROI. Boxplots of vibration angle prediction error are shown for a -9° (b) and -18° (c) vibration angle and a range of vibration amplitudes.

DISCUSSION

In this work, we show preliminary utility for a new imaging approach for detection of the vibration angle and, therefore, reconstruction of the 3D vibration vector. The advantage of this approach is that it can estimate 3D displacement using a typical OCT system, without the need for additional optical axes. This algorithmic strategy provides flexibility and enables new fundamental and therapeutic studies of hearing mechanics relative to existing OCT-V and our previous 3-channel OCT vibrometry approach. In particular, the proposed method enables reduced acquisition time, data size, and processing time, and is much simplified in design and maintenance compared with our previous 3-channel OCT-V system. The primary disadvantage of the technique is the reduced spatial resolution necessary to estimate the vibration angle (relative to the original B-Scan).

While we demonstrate our concept at low frequency and *in silico*, the approach may be extended into the range of auditory measurements. For mammalian hearing experiments, it is desirable to measure vibration amplitudes down to 1 nm or less. In this preliminary study, we show that we maintain sensitivity to vibration angle when the vibration amplitude is as low as 50 nm; while this sensitivity is useful in measurements of the cochlear mechanics in the mouse, greater sensitivity would allow application of the method in a wider range of experiments. Since we have tested our concept at a relatively low vibration frequency, however, we expect that if we perform this experiment at the best frequency range in the mouse apex (i.e. ~2-15 kHz), vibration amplitude sensitivity will improve by several orders of magnitude¹. For OCT magnitude data, it is also hypothesized that vibration amplitude sensitivity scales with optical resolution and signal-to-noise ratio, which may present additional avenues for investigation.

To apply our method to studies of cochlear mechanics, a higher scan frequency than that applied in this study is needed to capture vibration in the kilohertz range. The principle of the algorithm tested here is expected to transfer unchanged to higher stimulus frequencies. However, the scanner will either need to be replaced or driven in a different regime, which may present additional technical challenges. Many of the typical galvo mirrors used for scanning in OCT optical systems are capable of high frequency scanning as well as the MEMs mirrors which we use in our systems when driven above resonance, especially over such small angular ranges. Additional investigation is required to improve the algorithm as well as extending the technique to the frequency range needed for small animal models of hearing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Michael J. Serafino for helpful comments and technical support. AMW and this work are supported by the American Otological Society Fellowship Grant. BEA and JSO are supported by the NIH/NIDCD R01DC014450, R01DC013774, and R01DC017741 grant and NIH/NIBIB R01EB027113 grant.

REFERENCES

1. Kim, W., Kim, S., Huang, S., Oghalai, J. S. and Applegate, B. E. *Biomedical Optics Express* **10**, 4395-4410 (2019).
2. Gao, S.S., Wang, R., Raphael, P.D., Moayedi, Y., Groves, A.K., Zuo, J., Applegate, B.E. and Oghalai, J.S. *Journal of neurophysiology* **112**, 1192-1204 (2014).
3. Ren, T., He, W. and Kemp, D. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **113**, 9910-9915 (2016).
4. Dewey, J. B., Altoè, A., Shera, C. A., Applegate, B. E. and Oghalai, J. S. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **118**, e2025206118 (2021).
5. Lee, H.Y., Raphael, P.D., Xia, A., Kim, J., Grillet, N., Applegate, B.E., Bowden, A.K.E. and Oghalai, J.S. *Journal of Neuroscience* **36**, 8160-8173 (2016).
6. Cooper, N. P., Vavakou, A. and van der Heijden, M. *Nature communications* **9**, 1-12 (2018).
7. Meenderink, S.W., Lin, X., Park, B. H. and Dong, W. *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology*, 1-13 (2022).
8. Kim, W., Liu, D., Kim, S., Ratnayake, K., Macias-Escriva, F., Mattison, S., Oghalai, J.S. and Applegate, B.E. *Biomedical optics express* **13**, 2542-2553 (2022).

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Brian Frost]: It's a cool method. I understand how it's measuring the angle of motion in 2D but I don't understand how it could consistently measure the magnitude of motion. How is this method used to measure vector motion?

[Anna Wisniowiecki]: For now, we are proposing to use this method to measure only vibration angle. We are considering other approaches to see if we can measure both vibration angle and magnitude using a single data acquisition. However, this method is primarily meant to identify vibration angle and we would combine it with separate measurements including regular OCT vibrometry M-scans to get the other components of the motion vector.

[Sebastiaan Meenderink]: What are the limits to the motion amplitudes and angles that can be measured?

[Anna Wisniowiecki]: Vibration amplitude sensitivity depends upon the reflector SNR. If the SNR is very high, this method will be sensitive to smaller vibration amplitudes. The sensitivity also depends on the optical resolution and image sampling used. For vibration angle, this method can theoretically detect vibration axes over 180 degrees and the sensitivity is the same both laterally and axially since we are using a region of interest with similar resolution and sampling in both axes. Changes in this could create a sensitivity bias that may need to be accounted for. Practically, lateral sensitivity may also be affected by noise depending on scan stability.

[Scott Page]: This is an exciting and promising method, and I'm impressed by the low difference in estimated vs. ground truth angles!

What would you expect to see if two adjacent areas were moving at drastically different angles or magnitudes within overlapping ROIs, and would the result depend on the ground truth magnitude of each structure?

Why was a ROI size of 5x5 um chosen and what are the pros and cons of increasing or decreasing this size? Is it related to the 2.4 um lateral and axial optical resolution?

[Anna Wisniowiecki]: Interesting question. If there were vibration in multiple directions within an ROI, spatial frequencies corresponding to each direction would be modulated and affect the vibration angle estimation, since the simulated data used in the prediction algorithm only represents vibration along a single axis. The result would depend on the vibration amplitude and SNR of the reflectors inside the ROI. I would expect that the proposed algorithm would select the vibration angle that corresponds to the higher vibration amplitude (and SNR) assuming one vibration is significantly larger. If the vibrations were similar in scale, the mean square error would likely be similar for multiple simulated vibration angles and we could screen for this. In general and if we apply a statistical approach and use multiple ROIs to characterize a region of the organ of Corti, especially at lower amplitudes, we have to be cautious about screening ROI data/results for low SNR/vibration amplitude or as an outlier among the nearby ROIs.

One of the advantages of this approach compared with a 3-beam OCT system is that we can achieve higher resolution and, therefore, can measure smaller regions of the organ of Corti. We chose a 5 um ROI towards attempting to differentiate responses from different cell types in the organ and also to resolve the speckle which is required by this method. You can think of each ROI result (combined with vibration amplitude) as an average motion vector in that region. A disadvantage of this approach is reduced spatial resolution based on the size of the ROI. If we need to use a statistical method, spatial resolution is then reduced further.